

SYNTHETICAL EXPERIMENTS IN STEROLS AND BILE ACIDS

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2-Methyl-3-*sec*-isooctylcyclopentanone, an expected intermediate in the synthesis of Wieland's tricarboxylic acid and the sterols, has been synthesised.

To supply the final proof of the exact location of the long chain and to determine the nature of the locking of CD rings in the formulae accepted for the sterols and bile acids, the synthesis of the tricarboxylic acid (XVIII) (Wieland *et al.*, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1920, 108, 295; 1933, 216, 91; 1924, 134, 276; 1928, 177, 68) is imperatively necessary. With this end in view an attempt has been made to effect an actual synthesis of the acid (XVIII) with the secondary and tertiary carboxyl groups in their particular stereochemical configuration. A series of unsuccessful or incomplete attempts towards the same end has been recorded in literature (Baker, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1931, 1546; 1933, 811, 815; Bardhan and Banerji, *Science & Culture*, 1937, 2, 654; Banarjee, *ibid.*, 1938, 3, 678; Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 79).

Experiments were first begun with a view to preparing the ketone (XIII) which was expected to serve as an intermediate for synthetical purposes in two directions: firstly, the synthesis of Wieland's tricarboxylic acid (XVIII) and secondly, building up of the sterol structure according to the method adumbrated by Robinson, McQuillin and du Fau (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 53). The previous attempts, which have been made towards the synthesis of this ketone (XIII), are due to Robinson and Peak (*ibid.*, 1937, 1585), and Rydon (*ibid.*, 1939, 1544).

The present method, adopted for the preparation of the acid (III), is altogether different from that devised by Robinson and Peak (*loc. cit.*). It starts from 6-methyl-2-iodoheptane (I), prepared according to Clark (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 31, 111) with the only modification of reducing the methyl isohexyl ketone by sodium and moist ether, rectified spirit being added to the reaction mixture in order to minimise the formation of the corresponding pinacol (cf. *Bull. soc. chim. Roumania*, 1933, 13, 65). The iodide is converted in moderately good yield to the nitrile (II) by the usual procedure. Hydrolysis of the nitrile (II) presented considerable difficulties. Heating with 15% alcoholic caustic potash does not give satisfactory results. A 60% yield of the acid (III) is obtained by boiling the nitrile with 30% alcoholic caustic potash for a long time. The overall yield may be raised to above 80% by repeating the hydrolysis of the neutral fraction left behind. Having experienced the failure of G. M. Robinson's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 175; 1930, 745) when applied to the condensation product of the acid chloride (IV) with ethyl acetosuccinate (cf. Robinson and Peak, *loc. cit.*), attention was diverted towards the method of Nierenstein (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 2551), which was exploited by Huberland (*Ber.*, 1939, 72, 1216) in synthesising keto-acids.

The acid chloride (IV) is subjected to a series of reactions following exactly the conditions worked out by Haberland (*loc. cit.*) whereby the bromo-ketone (V) is obtained in excellent yield and its condensation with ethyl sodiomalonate in benzene proceeds smoothly. The hydrolysis of the resulting keto-diester (VI) with concentrated hydrochloric acid presents no difficulty. The ester (VIII) of the keto-acid (VII), prepared by alcohol-sulphuric acid method, on being subjected to Reformatsky's reaction with ethyl α -bromopropionate and zinc, affords the lactone (IX) in moderately good yield. The lactone ring is opened up with PBr_3 and ethyl alcohol. The resulting bromo-ester (X) in the crude state is then reduced with zinc dust and acetic acid according to the standard method giving rise to the adipic ester system (XI), which on ring-closure with molecularised sodium in benzene gives the cyclic β -ketonic ester (XII) imparting a greenish violet colour to ferric chloride solution in alcohol. The ketone (XIII) is then obtained by hydrolysing the above β -ketonic ester (XII) with 20% sulphuric acid. The ketone (XIII), thus obtained, characterised by its semicarbazone, has camphoraceous odour.

Before proceeding further with this costly material, it was thought desirable to perform some pilot experiments with the easily available 2-methylcyclopentanone (XIII, R=H) in order to find out the exact conditions for the actual synthesis.

The cyanohydrin of 2-methylcyclopentanone (XIII; R=H) has been prepared according to Clemo, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2629, but the yield is not uniform. Robinson and King (*ibid.*, 1941, 487) have reported a better method for the preparation of methylcyclopentanone cyanohydrin. The cyanohydrin (XIV; R=H) on being treated with thionyl chloride and pyridine (*cf.* Robinson and King, *loc. cit.*) is converted into the unsaturated nitrile (XV; R=H) in good yield. The next step, namely, the addition of hydrocyanic acid at the double bond in the unsaturated nitrile (XV; R=H), could not be realised, many attempts under various conditions turning out to be futile.

Again, 2-methyl- Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1-nitrile (XV; R=H) has been converted into 2-methyl-1-acetyl- Δ^1 -cyclopentene (XIX; R=H) by means of the Grignard reagent from methyl iodide according to the conditions of Butenandt and Schmidt-Thomé (*Ber.*, 1936, 71, 1487). Several unsuccessful attempts were made to add hydrocyanic acid to this unsaturated ketone under different conditions ("Organic Synthesis," 1930, Vol. X, p. 50; Lapworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 1219; Newmann, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 63, 2049).

Owing to the apparent similarity between Michael addition and hydrocyanic acid addition it was expected that the dicarboxylic acid (XVIII), which would have been obtained through HCN addition to the $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated nitrile (XV) or the $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone (XIX), should have its carboxylic groups in *trans* configuration in keeping with the expected configuration of the secondary and tertiary carboxyl groups in the tricarboxylic acid (XVIII) obtained from natural sources (*cf.* Linstead and Cook, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 958). On the other hand, if the *cis*-acid were produced, the *trans*-form could have been obtained by treatment of the *cis*-variety with sodium ethoxide (Bachmann and Struve, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 1262; Hückel and Goth, *Ber.*, 1925, 58, 447).

The present scheme of work may be represented thus :—

EXPERIMENTAL

Methylheptyl Cyanide (II).—A mixture of methylheptyl iodide (40 g.), potassium cyanide (22 g.), water (35 c.c.) and alcohol (115 c.c.) was heated under reflux on the water-bath for 12 hours, when the solution assumed a deep red colour. Next it was diluted with water and the light oil extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed, dried and the solvent removed. The residue when distilled passed over as a mobile liquid, b. p. 64-66°/6.5 mm., yield 17 g. Owing to the invariable contamination of this sample with the iodide it was not analysed.

2:6-Dimethylheptoic Acid (III).—A solution of the above nitrile (70 g.) in 30% methanolic caustic potash (58 g. KOH in 145 c. c. MeOH) was refluxed for 36 hours. Most of the alcohol was then driven off, diluted with water and extracted with ether. The evaporation of ether from the extract gave unhydrolysed nitrile which was again subjected to the above treatment. The alkaline mother-liquor was acidified with cold dilute sulphuric acid and the light oil extracted with ether, the ethereal layer washed and dried (Na₂SO₄). The solvent was then driven off and the residue when distilled came over at 108°/5.5 mm. as a clear mobile oil, yield 46 g. (Found: C, 67.88; H, 11.1. C₇H₁₄O₂ requires C, 68.35; H, 11.39 per cent).

The amide, prepared by the interaction of the acid chloride and liquor ammonia, when crystallised, had m. p. 97°. (Found: N, 8.86. C₇H₁₃ON requires N, 8.9 per cent).

Attempted Synthesis of the Keto-acid (VII) by *G. M. Robinson's Method*.—The acid chloride (IV) was prepared by treatment of the above acid (III, 40 g.) with 27 c. c. of thionyl chloride and the mixture let stand overnight. The excess of thionyl chloride was driven off in the water pump and the residue distilled when the desired product came over at 74°/5 mm., yield 38 g.

Sodium (25 g.) was granulated under xylene, washed with ether, and suspended in anhydrous ether (120 c. c.) and ethyl acetosuccinate (21.8 g.) gradually added, the solution of the sodium being completed by heating on the water-bath for 10 to 15 minutes. A solution of the acid chloride (15 g.), as prepared above, in ether was slowly added to the cooled mixture which was let stand for 24 hours and then

refluxed for 10 minutes. Then the product was isolated in the usual way and agitated for 5 hours with aqueous potassium hydroxide (1200 c. c. of 4% solution). After acidification with acetic acid and isolation by means of ether, it was submitted to the action of boiling 5% sulphuric acid for 4 hours, and the hydrolysis was completed by boiling with 8% sodium hydroxide solution for 1 hour. The solution was then acidified with dilute sulphuric acid and extracted with ether, the ethereal layer washed and dried (Na_2SO_4). The residue, left after the removal of the solvent, gave on distillation in vacuum 12 g. of the original acid (2:6-dimethylheptoleic acid, III) passing over at $106^\circ/5$ mm. leaving no significant higher boiling residue.

o-Bromomethyl-*sec*-isooctyl-ketone (V).—The above acid chloride (IV, 38 g.) in 25 c. c. of ether was added with cooling to a solution of diazomethane in dry ether (500 c. c.). After standing in the cold for one hour, hydrobromic acid (50 c. c. of 48%), was slowly added in the cold with shaking when a vigorous evolution of nitrogen took place and the mixture was kept overnight. The ethereal solution was then taken up, washed with sodium carbonate solution, water, dried and the solvent driven off. The residue on distillation gave the bromo-ketone, b. p. $95^\circ/5$ mm., yield 50.5 g. (Found: Br, 33.66. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{19}\text{OBr}$ requires Br, 34.04 per cent).

Condensation of Bromo-ketone (V) with Ethyl Sodiomalate.—To pulverised sodium (5.5 g.), taken under benzene and cooled in ice was added diethyl malonate (55 g.) and the mixture was left overnight. The bromo-ketone (V, 50 g.) was then slowly added with cooling and left for 1 hour. After refluxing for 16 hours on the water-bath, the mixture was cooled and water added, the benzene layer washed and dried. The residue, left after the evaporation of the solvent, gave the malonic ester derivative (VI, 56 g.), b. p. $168^\circ/5$ mm. (Found: C, 64.72; H, 9.53. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 64.97; H, 9.55 per cent).

δ -isohexylhomolaevulinic Acid (VII).—The above malonic ester derivative (VI, 58 g.) was refluxed with 250 c. c. of dilute hydrochloric acid (1:1) for 24 hours. The cooled mixture was then extracted with ether and the ethereal extract washed twice with sodium carbonate solution. From the ethereal solution 4 g. of the unchanged malonic ester derivative were recovered. The sodium carbonate extract was acidified with cold dilute sulphuric acid, extracted with ether and the ethereal layer washed and dried. After the evaporation of the solvent the residue was distilled in *vacuo* when a sweet-smelling, thick liquid (32 g.) came over at $150^\circ/3$ mm. (Found: C, 67.16; H, 10.22. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 67.29; H, 10.28 per cent).

The ester (VIII) of the above acid was prepared by refluxing a mixture of the keto-acid (33 g.), absolute alcohol (100 c. c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84; 6 c. c.) for 16 hours. After the usual working up, the ester was distilled in *vacuo*, b. p. $122^\circ/2$ mm., yield 32.5 g. (Found: C, 69.14; H, 10.62. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 69.42; H, 10.74 per cent).

Reformatsky's Reaction between the above Keto-ester (VIII) and Ethyl α -Bromopropionate.—A mixture of 24 g. of the above keto-ester (VIII), 9 c. c. of ethyl α -bromopropionate, 13 g. of zinc wool (washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, water, acetone and dried before use), 5 c. c. of thiophen-free benzene and 0.5 g. of iodine was heated under reflux on the water-bath. Within 10 to 15 minutes, the violet colour disappeared

and the solution became turbid. A violent reaction then ensued. The reaction sometimes became so violent that heating was temporarily stopped. After the abatement of the vigour of the reaction refluxing was continued for 1 hour, after which a fresh addition of 13 g. of zinc (activated) and 9 c. c. of ethyl α -bromopropionate and a few crystals of iodine was made and refluxing continued for 2 hours more when the reaction mixture assumed a greenish brown colour and a brown-coloured zinc complex was deposited at the bottom. The cooled reaction mixture was decomposed with acetic acid and methyl alcohol and diluted with water. The solution was then extracted with ether and the ether-benzene extract washed with dilute ammonia until the alkaline washings ceased to be coloured. After washing with water, the extract was dried, the solvents removed and the residue distilled when 16 g. of the lactone (IX) was obtained, b. p. $170^{\circ}/\frac{1}{4}$ mm. (Found: C, 68.18; H, 9.8. $C_{17}H_{30}O_2$ requires C, 68.45; H, 10.06 per cent):

Diethyl α -Methyl- β -sec-isooctyladipate (XI).—The above lactone (15 g.) was treated gradually with PBr_3 (25 g.) when the mixture assumed a deep red colour. The reaction mixture was kept overnight at the room temperature, the whole of the phosphorus pentabromide going into solution by that time. The dark red solution was poured into 50 c. c. of absolute alcohol, well cooled in ice. The solution was then refluxed on the water-bath for half-an-hour, cooled and poured into cooled water, the heavy layer extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, water, and dried. The residue left after the evaporation of the solvent was dried in vacuum and was dissolved in 150 c. c. glacial acetic acid and to this was added during 1 hour 32 g. of zinc dust, when the solution became rather hot. The mixture was then heated under reflux on a sand-bath for 20 hours. After decanting from the zinc sludge, the acetic acid solution was treated with ice-cooled caustic soda solution to neutralise most of the acetic acid, the solution diluted with water, and extracted with ether, the ether extract washed and dried. After the evaporation of the solvent, the residue on distillation in *vacuo* gave a halogen-free material (10.5 g.), b. p. $178^{\circ}/6$ mm. (Found: C, 69.26; H, 10.68. $C_{19}H_{36}O_4$ requires C, 69.51; H, 10.97 per cent).

Ethyl 2-Methyl-3-sec-isooctylcyclopentane-5-carboxylate (XII).—A mixture of 10 g. of the above dicarboxylic ester (XI), 1.5 g. of sodium and 30 c. c. of dry benzene was refluxed on the water-bath. After the whole of the sodium had gone into solution (1-1½ hours) the refluxing was continued for further half an hour. The solution assumed a red colour and after cooling it was decomposed with ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution, water and dried. The sodium carbonate extract was acidified and the separated oil collected. The evaporation of the solvent from the dried ethereal extract afforded 5.6 g. of the β -keto-ester with positive ferric reaction, b. p. $145^{\circ}/5$ mm. (Found: C, 72.65; H, 10.56. $C_{17}H_{30}O_3$ requires C, 72.34; H, 10.63 per cent).

2-Methyl-3-sec-isooctylcyclopentanone (XIII)—The above keto-ester (XII, 5.6 g.) together with the oil obtained by acidification of the sodium carbonate extract (see the previous experiment) was refluxed with hydrochloric acid (50 c. c., conc.) for 24 hours. The cooled solution was then extracted with ether, the ethereal layer washed and dried ($CaCl_2$).

After driving off the solvent the residue gave on distillation in *vacuo* 3 g. of the desired ketone, b. p. 122°/8 mm. having a camphoraceous odour. (Found: C, 79.62; H, 12.36. $C_{11}H_{20}O$ requires C, 80.0; H, 12.38 per cent).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared in the usual way, was crystallised from aqueous ethyl alcohol, m. p. 180-81°. (Found: N, 15.91. $C_{11}H_{18}ON_2$ requires N, 15.73 per cent).

2-Methyl- Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1-nitrile (XV; R=H).—To an ice-cold mixture of 2-methylcyclopentanone cyanohydrin (XIV, R=H 25 g.), prepared according to the method of Clemo (*loc. cit.*) and pyridine (32 c.c.) thionyl chloride (30 c. c.) was slowly added with shaking. After an hour the reaction mixture was heated on the steam-bath for 2 hours and cooled and decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid. After ether extraction, washing with dilute hydrochloric acid and water, the solvent was removed. The unsaturated nitrile (18 g.), b. p. 76-78°/20 mm., thus obtained, contained much dissolved sulphur which was removed by heating the nitrile in 50 c. c. of benzene with 2 g. of precipitated copper for an hour. After the usual procedure the nitrile came over on distillation as a clear, mobile liquid.

Attempted Hydrocyanic Acid Addition to the Nitrile (XV; R=H).—Potassium cyanide (28.7 g.) was dissolved in 95% alcohol (50 c. c.) and the solution cooled to room temperature. To this was added 15 g. of the nitrile (XV; R=H) and the solution was heated on the water-bath for half an hour. The cooled solution was largely diluted with water, extracted with ether, the ethereal layer washed twice with water and dried. After removing the solvent, the residue came over at 80-82°/24 mm. leaving no appreciable high boiling residue.

2-Methyl-1-acetyl- Δ^1 -cyclopentene (XIX; R=H).—The above unsaturated nitrile (XV; R=H, 15 g.) was added dropwise to a Grignard solution (3.5 g. of Mg. and 12 c. c. of MeI in 50 c. c. dry ether). The ether was driven off, dry thiophen-free benzene (50 c. c.) was added and the mixture refluxed for 6 hours. To the cooled reaction mixture was then added acetic acid (15 c. c.) and heating continued for half an hour. Water was then added and the mixture heated for further half an hour. The benzene layer was taken up, washed with water twice, dried and after the evaporation of the solvent the residue was distilled, when a clear liquid (12 g.) came over at 103°/5 mm. (Found: C, 76.93; H, 9.8. $C_9H_{12}O$ requires C, 77.42; H, 9.67 per cent).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared in the usual way, was crystallised from aqueous methyl alcohol, m. p. 200-201°. (Found: N, 23.3. $C_9H_{11}ON_2$ requires N, 23.2 per cent).

Attempted Hydrocyanic Acid Addition to the Unsaturated Ketone (XIX; R=H).—(a). According to the conditions of Lapworth (*loc. cit.*) a solution of the above ketone (12 g.) in 75 c. c. of boiling alcohol was mixed with a solution of potassium cyanide (13 g.) in 40 c. c. of hot water and the whole heated on the water-bath for 15 minutes. To the cooled mixture was added an aqueous solution of 5 g. of ferrous sulphate which served the purpose of converting the excess of potassium cyanide into ferricyanide as well as decomposing any cyanohydrin formed. The latter process was completed by raising the whole once more to the boiling point with constant shaking, care being taken that the liquid remained alkaline throughout. After filtration the liquid was diluted with water, extracted with ether, the ethereal extract dried and evaporated. The residue on distillation in vacuum was found to consist entirely of the unchanged ketone.

(b). According to the condition of Newmann (*loc. cit.*) a solution of 16.5 g. of potassium cyanide in 30 c. c. of water was added under the surface to a solution, at 55°, of 12.5 g. of the ketone (XIX; R = H) in 108 c. c. of alcohol. The addition was made over a period of 5 minutes with continued shaking. After 5 minutes the contents were warmed to 60°, the flask was wrapped with several towels and allowed to stand undisturbed for 1½ hours. After cooling, the solution was diluted with water, extracted with ether, the ethereal layer washed and dried. After the evaporation of the solvent the residue was distilled in vacuum when nothing except the unchanged ketone came over.

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